

2. Relationship between grain grade of the 1st primary branch (bottom) and yield. Andhra Pradesh, India.

Main and ratoon rice crop performance in mangrove swamps

M. P. Jones, *WARDA Regional Mangrove Swamp Rice Research Station, Rokupr, Sierra Leone*

In some of the tidal mangrove swamps of Sierra Leone and Guinea, very low

yields are obtained from second crop transplanted rice because farmers prefer long-duration photoperiod-sensitive varieties. The first crop matures in late Dec or early Jan. The second crop transplanted in Jan is subject to high levels of salt in the soil or to flooding at late growth stages.

We evaluated ratoon cropping as a

Performance of 16 rice varieties grown as main and ratoon crops in mangrove swamps in Rokupr, Sierra Leone.

Variety	Salt tolerance ratio	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)		Growth duration (d)	
		Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop
High tolerance					
Pa Foday Yoreh 260	0.69	2.7 ab	1.7 a	194	90
Pa Merr 108A	0.68	2.1 bc	0.9 c	197	94
Pa Fant 213	0.60	1.9 cd	0.9 c	197	99
IR4595-4-1-15	0.56	0.1 g	0.6 d	167	104
Pa Bathurst 32A	0.59	2.1 bc	0.6 d	180	98
Pokkali	0.75	0.7 fg	0.2 i	141	107
Moderate tolerance					
Improved Mashuri	0.52	0.8 f	0.5 de	174	92
CP4	0.49	2.7 ab	0.5 def	197	94
ROK5	0.54	2.7 ab	0.4 fgh	147	80
BD2	0.52	2.8 a	0.4 fgh	147	98
Low tolerance					
ROK10	0.39	2.6 ab	1.1 ab	197	95
BR51-49-6	0.38	1.2 ef	0.5 efg	164	81
BG90-2	0.31	0.9 ef	0.3 fgh	164	91
BG11-11	0.37	0.8 ef	0.3 hi	163	94
Djabon	0.33	1.4 de	0.3 hi	168	96
Bali Grodak	0.32	1.3 ef	0.3 hi	160	86
SE = 0.16					
CV (%)		16.8	12.7		

^aIn a column, values followed by identical letters are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

way to increase production at Rokupr during 1982-83.

In the ratoon study, 16 varieties produced grain (see table). The Pa Foday Yoreh 260 ratoon yield was 64.4% of the first crop yield. Other varieties that performed fairly well were ROK10, Pa Merr 108A, Pa Fant 213, IR4594-4-1-15, Pa Bathurst 32A, improved Mashuri, CP4, and BR51-49-6. Some varieties with low tolerance for salinity, such as ROK10, did fairly well because the ratoon crop matured before high soil salinity developed.

In the second crop study, only Pokkali was harvested, with 246 kg/ha grain yield. This highly salt-tolerant variety matured earlier than the other varieties, before the development of very high salt levels. The varieties which flowered late Apr to early May had empty spikelets. Average electrical conductivity during this period ranged from 15 to 18 mmho/cm for floodwater and 11 to 13 mmho/cm for topsoil.

Ratoon growth averaged 90 d. Photoperiod-sensitive Pa Merr 108A produced a ratoon crop in 94 d. This means that long-duration photoperiod-sensitive varieties harvested in Dec will produce a second ratoon crop in mid-March, much earlier than the normal second crop and well before the development of very high soil salinity. With the ratoon crop, land preparation, raising of seedlings, and transplanting are eliminated. □

Effect of time of lodging on rice productivity

B. Roy and J. N. Jha, *Agricultural Research Institute, Mithapur, Patna, Bihar, India*

In Bihar, rain between the last week of Sep and the first week of Oct helps boost rice productivity. But, when this rain is accompanied by gusty wind, crops lodge. In 1985, rain during the

second week of Oct was accompanied by high wind velocity. We assessed the loss in yield among cultivars of different maturity groups.

Maximum yield loss was 55% in IET7251 — the crop lodged 1 wk before flowering — followed by Sugandha, which lodged at booting (see table). Among the semidwarfs, maximum yield loss was in Radha that lodged 1 wk before flowering, followed by Pankaj that lodged either at flowering or at booting. Minimum yield loss was in Sujata that lodged 10 d after flowering. □

Effect of time of lodging on rice yields.

Variety	Duration (d)	Growth stage at lodging	Yield (t/ha)		Loss ^a (%)
			Lodged	No lodging	
<i>Dwarf (high yielding varieties)</i>					
Pankaj	155-160	Booting	3.5	6.5	46.8 e
Pankaj	155-160	Flowering	3.5	6.7	47.4 e
Radha	155-155	1 wk before flowering	3.1	6.2	49.9 f
Radha	150-155	1 wk after flowering	4.7	6.1	23.6 b
Sujata (BG90-2)	135-140	At flowering	3.5	5.4	35.7 c
Sujata (BG90-2)	135-140	10 d after flowering	4.4	5.2	18.2 a
Sita	135-140	1 wk after flowering	3.2	5.4	41.0 d
Sita	135-140	2 wk after flowering	3.2	5.4	41.6 d
<i>Tall plant type</i>					
Sugandha	Photoperiod sensitive	Booting	1.5	3.3	54.3 g
ET7251	155-160	1 wk before flowering	2.2	4.8	55.1 g

^a Values followed by identical letters are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

Seed dormancy in some short-duration rices

C. Kundu, A. Ghosh, and R. Ghosh, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, India

We assessed seed dormancy in 11 traditional rice varieties and 14 promising short-duration (90-110 d) breeding lines grown during aus (Mar-Sep), when preharvest seed sprouting in the field often follows monsoon rains. Seeds collected 30 d after flowering, coinciding with peak monsoon months, were dried to 13-14% moisture content. Germination at harvest and length and intensity of dormancy were measured. Dormancy intensity was determined by the time necessary to break dormancy with 50 °C heat treatment for 4 d. Dormancy length was days to attain 80% germination under ambient conditions.

Dormancy was 15-44 d in the traditional varieties and 27-54 d in the breeding lines. Many traditional varieties had strong seed dormancy; all the breeding lines except CR289-1208

Seed dormancy of 25 shortduration rices. Chinsurah, India.

	Germination (%) after 4 d heat treatment at 50° C	Dormancy	
		Intensity ^a	Period (d)
<i>Traditional</i>			
Bhutmuri	24	MD	30
Harimandir	nil	SD	40
Orissa aus	2	SD	40
Begunbichi	2	SD	42
Soni	78	WD	43
Panke	nil	SD	32
N22	2	SD	35
Baumal	32	MD	31
Joli	nil	SD	44
Juma	98	WD	41
China aus	100	WD	15
<i>Breeding lines</i>			
HPU741	74	WD	42
IR9708-51-1-2	72	WD	35
IR9729-67-3	88	WD	40
CR289-1208 (IET7255)	55	MD	54
Suweon	100	WD	28
BKNLR75091-CNT-B3 RST40-2-2	100	WD	37
IR8608-189-2-2-1-3	95	WD	30
Pusa 312	100	WD	38
OR165-93-15	78	WD	44
RP2086-74-6-1	100	WD	27
UPLRi7	90	WD	27
IR13204-24-16	90	WD	34
NSRP-1 Early	95	WD	30
RAU4045-10	85	WD	33

^a WD = weakly dormant, MD = moderately dormant, SD = strongly dormant.

(IET7255) were weakly dormant (see table). China aus attained 100%

germination after heat treatment and had very weak dormancy. □

Leaf chlorophyll content of submerged rice seedlings

S. Gupta, P. Sengupta, and B. Banerji, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah 712102, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

We assessed leaf chlorophyll content of seedlings of six rice varieties (B-9c-Md-3-3, CN540, CR126-42-1, FR13A, Mohon, and OC1393) grown in pots under submerged and nonsubmerged conditions.

Seedlings were raised in 25-cm-diam earthen pots at 50 seeds/pot with 8 replications. At 10 d after seeding (DAS), 4 pots/variety were submerged in 50-cm water for 10 d, then treated normally to 35 DAS. Leaf chlorophyll